

ON THE WEAKLY PRIME-ADDITIVE NUMBERS WITH LENGTH 4

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Abstract

In 1992, Erdős and Hegyvári showed that for any prime p , there exist infinitely many length 3 weakly prime-additive numbers divisible by p . In 2018, Fang and Chen showed that for any positive integer m , there exist infinitely many length 3 weakly prime-additive numbers divisible by m if and only if 8 does not divide m . Assuming the existence of a prime in certain arithmetic progressions with prescribed primitive root, which is true under the Generalized Riemann Hypothesis (GRH), we show that for any positive integer m , there exist infinitely many length 4 weakly prime-additive numbers divisible by m . We also present another related result analogous to the length 3 case shown by Fang and Chen.

1. Introduction

A number n with at least 2 distinct prime divisors is called *prime-additive* if $n = \sum_{p|n} p^{a_p}$ for some $a_p > 0$. If additionally, $p^{a_p} < n \leq p^{a_p+1}$ for all $p|n$, then n is called *strongly prime-additive*. In 1992, Erdős and Hegyvári [2] stated a few examples and conjectured that there are infinitely many strongly prime-additive numbers. However, this problem was and is still far from being solved. For example, not even the infinitude of prime-additive numbers is known. Therefore they introduced the following weaker version of prime-additive numbers.

Definition 1. A positive integer n is said to be *weakly prime-additive* if n has at least 2 distinct prime divisors, and there exists distinct prime divisors p_1, \dots, p_t of n and positive integers a_1, \dots, a_t such that $n = p_1^{a_1} + \dots + p_t^{a_t}$. The minimal value of such t is defined to be the *length* of n , denoted as κ_n .

Note that if n is a weakly prime-additive number, then $\kappa_n \geq 3$. So we call a weakly prime-additive number with length 3 a *shortest weakly prime-additive number*.

Erdős and Hegyvári [2] showed that for any prime p , there exist infinitely many weakly prime-additive numbers divisible by p . In fact, they showed that these weakly prime-additive numbers can be taken to be shortest weakly prime-additive in their proof. They also showed that the number of shortest weakly prime-additive numbers up to some integer N is at least $c(\log N)^3$ for a sufficiently small constant $c > 0$.

In 2018, Fang and Chen [3] showed that for any positive integer m , there exist infinitely many shortest weakly prime-additive numbers divisible by m if and only if 8 does not divide m . This is Theorem 5 stated in this paper. They also showed that for any positive integer m , there exist infinitely many weakly prime-additive numbers with length $\kappa_n \leq 5$ that are divisible by m . In the same paper, Fang and Chen posted four open problems. The first one inquires whether, for any positive integer m , there are infinitely many weakly prime-additive numbers n with $m|n$ and $\kappa_n = 4$. In Theorem 1 of this paper, we confirm this is true, assuming the existence of a prime in certain arithmetic progressions with prescribed primitive root (see assumption (*) on p.2). This assumption is known to hold under the Generalized Riemann Hypothesis (GRH).

Finally, it was also shown in [3] that for any distinct primes p, q , there exists a prime r and infinitely many a, b, c such that $pqr|p^a + q^b + r^c$. In Theorem 2, we extend this result analogously to four distinct primes, subject to mild congruence conditions, assuming the same assumption as mentioned above.

2. Main Results

Assumption (*). Let $1 \leq a \leq f$ be positive integers with $(a, f) = 1$ and $4|f$. Let g be an odd prime dividing f such that $\left(\frac{g}{a}\right) = -1$ with (\cdot) being the Kronecker symbol. Then there exists a prime p such that $p \equiv a \pmod{f}$ and g is a primitive root of p .

It is known that (*) is a consequence of the Generalized Riemann Hypothesis (GRH), see Corollary 1 in the next section for details. Under the assumption (*), we have the following.

Theorem 1. *Assume (*). For any positive integer m , there exist infinitely many weakly prime-additive numbers n with $m|n$ and $\kappa_n = 4$.*

Note that if a positive integer n can be expressed in the form of $n = p^a + q^b + r^c + s^d$ for some distinct primes p, q, r, s , and positive integers a, b, c, d such that $p, q, r, s|n$, then p, q, r, s are all odd primes. We have the following theorem as a partial converse.

Theorem 2. *Assume (*). For any distinct odd primes p, q, r with one of them $\equiv 3$ or $5 \pmod{8}$, there exist infinitely many prime s and infinitely many positive*

integers a, b, c, d such that

$$pqrs|p^a + q^b + r^c + s^d.$$

This is analogous to Theorem 1.4 in [3], which says that for any given distinct primes p, q , there exists a prime $r > \max\{p, q\}$ and infinitely many triples (a, b, c) of positive integers such that $pqr|p^a + q^b + r^c$.

3. Preliminaries

Lemma 1 ([4, Thm 72]). (The Fermat-Euler Theorem) *Let a, n be coprime positive integers. Then*

$$a^{\phi(n)} \equiv 1 \pmod{n},$$

where ϕ is the Euler totient function.

We will use the Kronecker Symbol (\cdot) , which is a generalization of the Legendre symbol. Precisely, this is defined as follows. Let a, b be integers. If $b = 0$ or $b = \pm 1$, we define

$$\left(\frac{a}{0}\right) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } a = \pm 1 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad \text{and} \quad \left(\frac{a}{\pm 1}\right) = \begin{cases} \pm 1 & \text{if } a < 0 \\ 1 & \text{if } a \geq 0. \end{cases}$$

For the remaining cases, let $b = \pm p_1^{e_1} \cdots p_k^{e_k}$ be the prime factorization of b . We then define

$$\left(\frac{a}{b}\right) = \left(\frac{a}{\pm 1}\right) \prod_{i=1}^k \left(\frac{a}{p_i}\right)^{e_i},$$

where for any prime p ,

$$\left(\frac{a}{p}\right) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } a \text{ is a quadratic residue modulo } p \text{ and } a \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p} \\ -1 & \text{if } a \text{ is a quadratic nonresidue modulo } p \\ 0 & \text{if } a \equiv 0 \pmod{p} \end{cases}$$

is the Legendre symbol.

Whenever we write $(\frac{a}{b})$ for some integers a, b , it refers to the Kronecker symbol. We will need the following properties of the Kronecker symbol. See, for example, [1, p. 289-290] for a proof.

Lemma 2. *Let a, b, c be any nonzero integers, and p, q be any odd primes. Let a', b' be the odd part of a and b , respectively. Then we have:*

$$1. \left(\frac{ab}{c}\right) = \left(\frac{a}{c}\right) \left(\frac{b}{c}\right) \text{ unless } c = -1;$$

2. $\left(\frac{a}{b}\right) = (-1)^{\frac{a'-1}{2} \frac{b'-1}{2}} \left(\frac{b}{a}\right)$;
3. $\left(\frac{-2}{p}\right) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } p \equiv 1, 3 \pmod{8} \\ -1 & \text{if } p \equiv 5, 7 \pmod{8}; \end{cases}$
4. $\left(\frac{a}{p}\right) \equiv a^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \pmod{p}$;
5. $\left(\frac{p}{q}\right) = \left(\frac{q}{p}\right)$ unless $p \equiv q \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$;
6. If $p \equiv q \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, $\left(\frac{p}{q}\right) = -\left(\frac{q}{p}\right)$.

On primes in arithmetic progressions, we have the celebrated Dirichlet’s theorem. See, for example, [1, Chapter 1] for a proof.

Theorem 3. (Dirichlet’s Theorem) *If a, d are coprime positive integers, then there are infinitely many primes p such that $p \equiv a \pmod{d}$.*

Under GRH, we have the following generalization.

Theorem 4 ([5, Thm 1.3]). *Let $1 \leq a \leq f$ be positive integers with $(a, f) = 1$. Let g be an integer that is not equal to -1 or a square, and let $h \geq 1$ be the largest integer such that g is an h th power. Write $g = g_1 g_2^2$ with g_1 square free, and $g_1, g_2 \in \mathbb{Z}$. Let*

$$\beta = \frac{g_1}{(g_1, f)} \text{ and } \gamma_1 = \begin{cases} (-1)^{\frac{\beta-1}{2}}(f, g_1) & \text{if } \beta \text{ is odd;} \\ 1 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Let $\pi_g(x; f, a)$ be the number of primes $p \leq x$ such that $p \equiv a \pmod{f}$ and g is a primitive root \pmod{p} . Then, assuming GRH, we have

$$\pi_g(x; f, a) = \delta(a, f, g) \frac{x}{\log x} + O_{f,g} \left(\frac{x \log \log x}{\log^2 x} \right),$$

where

$$\delta(a, f, g) = \frac{A(a, f, h)}{\phi(f)} \left(1 - \left(\frac{\gamma_1}{a}\right) \frac{\mu(|\beta|)}{\prod_{\substack{p|\beta \\ p|h}}(p-1) \prod_{\substack{p|\beta \\ p \nmid h}}(p^2 - p - 1)} \right)$$

if one of the following holds:

- $g_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$,
- $g_1 \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$ and $8|f$
- $g_1 \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$ and $4|f$.

Otherwise, we have

$$\delta(a, f, g) = \frac{A(a, f, h)}{\phi(f)}.$$

Here μ is the Möbius function, (\cdot) is the Kronecker symbol, and

$$A(a, f, h) = \prod_{p|(a-1, f)} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p}\right) \prod_{\substack{p \nmid f \\ p|h}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p-1}\right) \prod_{\substack{p \nmid f \\ p \nmid h}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p(p-1)}\right)$$

if $(a-1, f, h) = 1$, and $A(a, f, h) = 0$ otherwise.

Corollary 1. *Assume GRH. Let a, f, g be as above and $\left(\frac{g}{a}\right) = -1$. There exists a prime p such that $p \equiv a \pmod{f}$ and g is a primitive root of p . In other words, assumption $(*)$ holds true under GRH.*

Proof. This corresponds to a special case of Theorem 4, with our specific conditions on $a, f, g, \beta = h = 1, \gamma_1 = g$. Notice that

$$\delta(a, f, g) = \frac{2}{\phi(f)} \prod_{p|(a-1, f)} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p}\right) \prod_{\substack{p \nmid f \\ p \nmid h}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p(p-1)}\right) > 0.$$

□

Remark 1. This shows that our result also follows from GRH, which is a much stronger assumption than $(*)$.

Theorem 5 ([3, Cor 1.1]). *For any positive integer m , there exist infinitely many shortest weakly prime-additive numbers n with $m|n$ if and only if 8 does not divide m .*

4. Proof of Theorem 1

We first prove the following weaker version of Theorem 1.

Theorem 6. *Assume $(*)$. For any positive integer m , there exist infinitely many weakly prime-additive numbers n with $m|n$ and $\kappa_n \leq 4$.*

Proof. Let m be a positive integer. Write $m = 2^k m_1$ with $(m_1, 2) = 1$ and $k \geq 0 \in \mathbb{Z}$. Without loss of generality, we assume $k \geq 3$. In fact, if the theorem holds when m is replaced by $2^{\max\{3, k\}} m$, then the theorem holds for m . We will construct a family of distinct primes p, q, r, s and positive integers a, b, c such that each of m, p, q, r, s divides n , where $n := p^a + q^b + r^c + s$.

Let p be an odd prime such that $(p, m) = 1$. By the Chinese Remainder Theorem and Theorem 3, there exists an odd prime q such that

$$q \equiv 1 \pmod{2^k p} \text{ and } q \equiv -1 \pmod{m_1}.$$

Similarly, we can use the same two theorems to conclude that there exists an odd prime r such that

$$r \equiv 3 \pmod{2^k} \text{ and } r \equiv 1 \pmod{pqm_1}.$$

Applying the Chinese Remainder Theorem again, there exists a unique integer s_0 such that $1 \leq s_0 \leq pqrm$ and

$$\begin{aligned} s_0 &\equiv -5 \pmod{2^k} \\ s_0 &\equiv -1 \pmod{m_1} \\ s_0 &\equiv -2 \pmod{pqr}. \end{aligned}$$

Note that $(s_0, pqrm) = 1$.

Since $k \geq 3$, we have $r \equiv 3 \pmod{2^k}$ and $s_0 \equiv -5 \pmod{2^k}$. This implies that $r \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$ and $s_0 \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$. Using Lemma 2, we observe that

$$\left(\frac{r}{s_0}\right) = \left(\frac{s_0}{r}\right) (-1)^{\frac{s_0-1}{2} \frac{r-1}{2}} = -\left(\frac{s_0}{r}\right) = -\left(\frac{-2}{r}\right) = -1.$$

Here we used $s_0 \equiv -2 \pmod{r}$ as $s_0 \equiv -2 \pmod{pqr}$. Therefore, applying Corollary 1 with $a = s_0$, $f = pqrm$ and $g = r$, there exists an odd prime s such that $s \equiv s_0 \pmod{pqrm}$, and r is a primitive root of s . Consequently, s satisfies all the previously mentioned congruence relations satisfied by s_0 . Furthermore, there exists a positive integer c_0 such that

$$r^{c_0} \equiv -2 \pmod{s}.$$

Note that by construction, p, q, r, s are all distinct odd primes.

Now for any positive integer c' , take

$$c = (p-1)(q-1)(r-1)\phi(m)c' + c_0.$$

For any positive odd integer b' , take

$$b = \frac{1}{4}(r-1)(s-1)b'.$$

Since $r \equiv 3 \pmod{2^k}$ and $s \equiv -5 \pmod{2^k}$, we have $r, s \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, ensuring that b is odd. For any positive integer a' , take

$$a = (q-1)(r-1)(s-1)\phi(m)a',$$

where ϕ is the Euler totient function. Finally, let

$$n = p^a + q^b + r^c + s.$$

Note that we have the following congruence conditions:

1. As $q \equiv r \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$, $s \equiv -2 \pmod{p}$, we have

$$n \equiv p^a + q^b + r^c + s \equiv 0 + 1 + 1 - 2 \equiv 0 \pmod{p}.$$

2. Since $q - 1|a$, Lemma 1 implies that $p^a \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$. Hence we have

$$n \equiv p^a + q^b + r^c + s \equiv 1 + 0 + 1 - 2 \equiv 0 \pmod{q}.$$

3. Similarly, $p^a \equiv 1 \pmod{r}$ as $r - 1|a$. Since $q \equiv 1 \pmod{2^k p}$, we have $q \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$. Applying Lemma 2 with $r \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$ and $r \equiv 1 \pmod{q}$,

$$q^b \equiv (q^{\frac{1}{2}(r-1)})^{\frac{1}{2}(s-1)b'} \equiv \left(\frac{q}{r}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}(s-1)b'} \equiv \left(\frac{r}{q}\right) \equiv \left(\frac{1}{q}\right) \equiv 1 \pmod{r}.$$

So we have

$$n \equiv p^a + q^b + r^c + s \equiv 1 + 1 + 0 - 2 \equiv 0 \pmod{r}.$$

4. Similarly, $p^a \equiv q^b \equiv 1 \pmod{s}$. As $r^c \equiv -2 \pmod{s}$, we have

$$n \equiv p^a + q^b + r^c + s \equiv 1 + 1 - 2 + 0 \equiv 0 \pmod{s}.$$

5. As $\phi(m)|a$, Lemma 1 gives us $p^a \equiv 1 \pmod{m}$. Since b is odd and $q \equiv -1 \pmod{m_1}$, we get $q^b \equiv -1 \pmod{m_1}$. Together with $r \equiv 1 \pmod{m_1}$ and $s \equiv -1 \pmod{m_1}$, we have

$$n \equiv p^a + q^b + r^c + s \equiv 1 - 1 + 1 - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{m_1}.$$

6. Since $p^a \equiv 1 \pmod{m}$, $q \equiv 1 \pmod{2^k}$, $r \equiv 3 \pmod{2^k}$ and $s \equiv -5 \pmod{2^k}$, we have

$$n \equiv p^a + q^b + r^c + s \equiv 1 + 1 + 3 - 5 \equiv 0 \pmod{2^k}.$$

As a result, $n = p^a + q^b + r^c + s$ is weakly prime additive and is divisible by m . Since a', c' can be any positive integers, b' can be any positive odd integer and p can be any arbitrary odd prime that is coprime to m , we have constructed infinitely many weakly prime-additive n with length at most 4. \square

Remark 2. In the above construction, s can be raised to any d -th power for any positive integer $d \equiv 1 \pmod{\phi(pqrm)}$.

Together with Theorem 5, we can now prove Theorem 1.

Proof of Theorem 1. Let m be a positive integer. By Theorem 6, there exist infinitely many weakly prime-additive numbers with length ≤ 4 such that they are divisible by $8m$. Since $8|8m$, Theorem 5 implies that these numbers cannot be shortest weakly prime-additive, and hence they are all weakly prime-additive numbers with length 4. \square

5. Proof of Theorem 2

Let p, q, r be distinct odd primes, with one of them, WLOG say r , satisfying $r \equiv 3$ or $5 \pmod{8}$. Let k be the positive integer such that $\frac{(p-1)(q-1)}{2^k}$ is odd. We denote this value as $A = \frac{(p-1)(q-1)}{2^k}$ and set $f = 8Apqr$. By the Chinese Remainder Theorem, there exists a unique integer s_0 such that $1 \leq s_0 \leq f$ and

$$\begin{aligned} s_0 &\equiv 3 \pmod{8} \\ s_0 &\equiv -2 \pmod{Apqr}. \end{aligned}$$

Using Lemma 2 and the condition that $r \equiv 3$ or $5 \pmod{8}$, we have

$$\left(\frac{r}{s_0}\right) = (-1)^{\frac{r-1}{2} \frac{s_0-1}{2}} \left(\frac{s_0}{r}\right) = (-1)^{\frac{r-1}{2}} \left(\frac{-2}{r}\right) = -1.$$

Applying Theorem 3 with the above a, f , and $g = r$, there exists an odd prime s such that

$s \equiv s_0 \pmod{8Apqr}$ and r is a primitive root of s . In other words, r generates $(\mathbb{Z}/(s\mathbb{Z}))^*$ and hence there exists $0 < c_0 < s - 1$ such that

$$r^{c_0} \equiv -2 \pmod{s}.$$

Since $s \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$, we have $\left(\frac{-2}{s}\right) = 1$, implying that c_0 must be even.

Now by the Chinese Remainder Theorem, take any positive integer c such that

$$\begin{aligned} c &\equiv c_0 \pmod{\frac{s-1}{2}} \\ c &\equiv 0 \pmod{(p-1)(q-1)}. \end{aligned}$$

This is feasible because $s \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$ and $s \equiv -2 \pmod{A}$, ensuring that $\left(\frac{s-1}{2}, (p-1)(q-1)\right) = 1$. Since c_0 is even and $\frac{s-1}{2}$ is odd, this makes $c \equiv c_0 \pmod{s-1}$. Thus, we obtain $r^c \equiv -2 \pmod{s}$ and $r^c \equiv 1 \pmod{pq}$.

Finally, for any positive integers a, b, d such that $(q-1)(r-1)(s-1)|a$, $(p-1)(r-1)(s-1)|b$, $d \equiv 1 \pmod{(p-1)(q-1)(r-1)}$, we have the following:

$$p^a + q^b + r^c + s^d \equiv 0 + 1 + 1 - 2 \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$$

$$p^a + q^b + r^c + s^d \equiv 1 + 0 + 1 - 2 \equiv 0 \pmod{q}$$

$$p^a + q^b + r^c + s^d \equiv 1 + 1 + 0 - 2 \equiv 0 \pmod{r}$$

$$p^a + q^b + r^c + s^d \equiv 1 + 1 - 2 + 0 \equiv 0 \pmod{s}$$

Therefore, for any positive integers a, b, c, d as above, we have

$$pqrs|p^a + q^b + r^c + s^d.$$

□

References

- [1] R. G. Ayoub, *An Introduction to the Analytic Theory of Numbers*, Amer. Math. Soc., Providence, 1963.
- [2] P. Erdős and N. Hegyvári, On prime-additive numbers, *Stud. Sci. Math. Hung.* **27** (1992), 207-212.
- [3] J. H. Fang and Y. G. Chen, On the shortest weakly prime-additive numbers, *J. Number Theory* **182** (2018), 258-270.
- [4] G. H. Hardy and E. M. Wright, *An Introduction to the Theory of Numbers*, Oxford university press, Oxford, 1979.
- [5] P. Moree, On primes in arithmetic progression having a prescribed primitive root. II, *Funct. Approx. Comment. Math.* **39.1** (2008), 133-144.